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Novel Coronavirus 2019: Its Emergence, Mechanism of Infection and Possible Treatment Methods

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Abstract

This paper examined the emergence of coronavirus disease of 2019 (COVID-19), its methods of spread and treatment. Data were obtained from secondary sources and were analysed qualitatively. The severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2019 (SARS-COV -2) with its typical crown-like spikes on the outer surface belongs to the β -group of the coronaviridae family. The virus causes the coronavirus disease of 2019 (COVID-19), which emerged from the Wuhan Province of China. Millions of cases and hundreds of thousands of deaths have been reported around the world. The glycoprotein spikes on the outer surface are used for attachment and entry into the host cells. The SARS- coronavirus employs angiotensin –converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) as receptor. It attacks the respiratory system particularly and most infected people develop mild to moderate illness however, severe cases may lead to death. It is mainly transmitted through contact with infected body fluids. There are no anti-viral medications or vaccines for the treatment of COVID-19. Though, some drugs and vaccines are being produced and tested presently, treatment is based mainly on symptoms displayed by infected individuals and it is normally through the administration of combination drugs. The paper suggested that potential drugs for the treatment of COVID-19 must be formulated to target specific areas in the SARS-COV-2 in order to be effective against the virus.

Keywords: Novel, COVID-19, emergence, mechanism of infection, possible treatment.